

THE FEASIBLE PROJECT AS A METHODOLOGICAL WAY OF SOLVING ONE'S OWN NEEDS IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES

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Abstract

The present article displays a vision of three active researchers, who in their work and professional experience have directed research projects from the modality of Feasible Project, in which their positions have been imbricated towards research when the purpose is to look for alternative solutions by the operative way, that is to say, solutions in practice. Its scenarios have been diverse, as it has been used for Specialization studies in areas of project management, risk and occupational health, early education, among other postgraduate studies of the different areas of knowledge in Social Sciences. In that order, there has been a transformation of the elucidation of the Feasible Project, which has been presented in this written production, since its incursion as a method has allowed to define with greater precision its scopes, its structuring, its projection and successes in the formative contribution of graduate students.

Keywords: Feasible project, method, resolution, needs, social sciences.

Methodical Accuracy of the Feasible Project from its Dilucidation

There are countless methodological alternatives that today respond to the solution of problematic situations in the field of social sciences. However, it is necessary to reflect on scientific research and for it to be recognised as the procedure and systematisation in which science manages to prevail over knowledge. In other words, knowledge, in turn, has different edges of anchorage, from which it can be appreciated, ranging from theoretical successes to practical dispositions.

In this sense, it refers to research in its broadest sense, as indicated by Gandía and Magallanes (2013) to the set of planned actions that aim to solve problems of scientific interest. It is from this definition, which is then added, that the methodology has contributed to the study of the different methods that guide research in the treatment and solution of these problems. In addition, it is understandable that also the methods are the way for the contribution; be it theoretical, practical or both, that with its efficient adaptation reaches the research intention. In the process of research, the sense that the researcher gives to the processing of information is enhanced. For this reason, the selected method must converge from the multiple elements and empirical referents coming from the vision, experience and domains that it contributes in the construction of the object of knowledge.

In accordance with what has been described, scientific work, in its procedural improvement, has been validating methods that are increasingly efficient and pertinent with the diverse forms of knowledge that today contribute both to the scientific community in which the research is registered and to the studied reality. From there, it is given a proximity of increasing interest to the solution of specific practical problems, so that the *Feasible Projects* are presented as an applicable

way in the resolution of problems from the generation of a proposal raised from feasible actions. For the project director as well as for the student, the challenge is to carry out a research process that integrates theoretical and practical support.

Although much has been said about its methodological constitution, it is propitious to distinguish the Feasible Project from the definition made by the Universidad Pedagógica Experimental Libertador (2003, p.16) as "A study that consists in the investigation, elaboration and development of a proposal of a viable operative model to solve problems, requirements or needs of organizations or social groups". Therefore, the proposal is posed from that definition given by the university, as the formulation of policies, programs, technologies, methods or processes that only make sense in the scope of their needs.

For his part, Hurtado (2000, p.42) defines the Feasible Project as projective research, which: "Leads to inventions, programs, designs that satisfy a verified need in an organizational or social diagnosis". In other words, priority is given to the creation of a proposal for action leading to the resolution of a problem or need detected in a diagnosis.

From the disposition of the given definitions, it can be iterated that in the Feasible Project its possibility of execution allows the achievement of the objectives from the detection of needs determined in the diagnosis, which is an unavoidable part of this method. Likewise, its reliable scope can be in the creation of the proposal or go towards its execution. This scope will only respond to the interest assumed by the researcher. From the point of view of the research authors of this written production, the formative academic experience in research from this method must rebound to the fact that the students of the different specializations are capable of being introduced into the process of scientific research proper to the social sciences, by understanding the different stages of the process of construction of a Feasible Project, since they are necessary for its systematization. Also, not less important, students must become able to understand the relationship between theory and method present in the process of this research modality. The authors agree that it is necessary to learn, propose and evaluate different strategies depending on the design that innovate and enrich the scenario for which the operative solution is presented.

Implicit Implications of the Feasible Project from its Procedure

However, from the practical relevance of the Feasible Project, it is relevant that the methodological process responds to some basic stages, which indistinctly of the paradigm in which the study is inscribed and its instrumental orientation must correspond with a diagnosis or real situation, feasibility or possibility of execution and design or foundation of the proposal. In this regard, Ruiz Bolívar (1998) raises the issue of diagnosis as the specification of detected needs. Therefore, for this stage it will be necessary to consider it as a concrete objective. In that order of the process, is the feasibility, which according to Salcedo (2003) refers to the real possibility of execution of the proposal, that is, functional possibility, in terms of willingness to change and availability of resources and other elements that the researcher adose as necessary for its execution.

And the creation stage, which is the one that responds to the design of the proposal, is proposed by Pallares (2002) as the product of the processing of the inputs obtained through the needs assessment, through the application of information gathering instruments selected by the researcher. It should be noted that its basic form of presentation is a prospective plan, i.e., it can be carried out from a planning stage where actions are formulated at established times, the necessary resources are indicated and these aspects are coordinated so that they can be adapted to the expected goals or results. In addition, depending on the specific objectives, the design may lead to the execution and evaluation of the proposal. Therefore, if this were the intention of the researcher, they would be presented previously in specific objectives.

From the approaches made around the Feasible Project as a methodical route, its sustainability can be reconsidered, which allows its methodological use to become an alternative of great attention and interest in research. However, it is greatly enhanced in postgraduate studies such as Specializations, when the curricular purpose of the program is aimed at corresponding with the greater mastery in practice of the disciplinary area to which that Specialization refers. In addition, it is added that this research alternative has a purpose of immediate use, which is the execution of the proposal. The researchers authors of this written production agree in affirming that the process of the student in his methodological domain and the process of the professor director of the project will be successful from the possibility of creation as innovation, as well as from the vision of the social, personal and institutional contribution in which the experience of the Feasible Project is carried out. The student in his formative process of investigation from this methodical modality with an application approach, requires a process of greater intervention in the studied scenario, only in this way will proposals be created with action plans that are viable to execute and that produce improvements or substantial changes in those studied scenarios.

However, after its scope of application, many adjustments have been made to the Feasible Project to be used as a research modality at other levels of study. Meanwhile, the appreciation in this written production is to expose some of the attachments that respond to the Feasible Project and that are relieved from the professional experience of the research authors and the informative comparability provided in the documentary review made. In this sense, in a succinct way the systemic axis is raised that must conform a study from the Feasible Project method:

In the first instance, a problematic situation is emphasized. In this section the researcher must make an approach to the reality under study, there from his position presents the empirical references that constitute the discrepancies with the ideological criteria of the topic of interest, whether in terms of precariousness or nullity of actions, strategies or procedural criteria among so many other elements that glimpse a problem with urgency of operative solution. Therefore, the research purpose should be to propose a practical solution or the satisfaction of needs that are already felt from the viewpoint of the researcher.

In the second instance, objectivation is exalted. In that aspect, the objectives are conformed, which are instituted from the generation of a proposal for action. To this end, its concrete objectives correspond to a systematic process that will address the diagnosis, feasibility and design; the latter

as actions as a consequence of the previous stages. In that order, it is worth distinguishing that if it is of interest to the researcher, the objectives of execution and evaluation of the proposal can be added, since from the genesis of the Feasible Project there is the establishment of pertinence and viability, with which these added objectives have the purpose of proving or valuing that the Project, when carried out, effectively solves the research problem.

In the third instance, the method is weighted. Here it must be referred that the Feasible Project must mean for the essence of its methodological feasibility, how it is going to obtain the information; in this case it may be supported as field or documentary research. How it will guide the application of instruments; in this case it may be qualitative or quantitative.

In the fourth instance, the diagnosis is recommended. This is considered crucial in the Feasible Project, as it will verify the needs detected. At this stage, the information is obtained and its results are presented in a process of analysis of the discrepancies and their hierarchization. The process concludes by presenting the diagnosis of needs as a requirement for the design of the proposal. It is worth noting that, as Kaufman (1991) indicates, the identification of needs is an analysis of discrepancies determined by the two extreme positions of: Where is currently in the reality found? and Where should it be?

The fifth instance attends to the design of the proposal. This stage starts from the diagnosis made, since the design is based on the generation of an action plan that encompasses the proposal; its construction will contain objectives, strategies, activities, resources and evaluation. That is to say, a planning that responds in offering an operative solution to the posed problem.

And the last instance is the feasibility analysis. Although this is set out in a specific objective, which means that it requires the obtaining of information, it is to be assumed that its results must be considered for the real possibility of execution of the proposal, in terms of availability of human resources, infrastructure, economic resources, materials, equipment or any other that the researcher believes necessary for the implementation of the action plan designed.

The researcher is exhorted to present at the end if he only generated the design of the proposal, to close the Feasible Project with a section that integrates his transformed vision of the topic or object of study and makes his recommendations derived from the research construction, from which he presented his theoretical referential aspects, obtained a diagnosis of needs and designed a plan of actions to present that proposal. Now, if it went beyond presenting the proposal and outlined in the concrete objectives its execution and evaluation, the Feasible Project should close with its conclusions on the process of realization and effectiveness of the action plan, where it can also link the theoretical and practical and its correspondence in the strengths, threats and opportunities of its proposal.

Colophon

In order to finish this production written around the Feasible Project it is inevitable to put before the formative vision in research, which requires all postgraduate students in the different studies of this level. In this regard, it has been concluded from the positions of the research authors that the research process undertaken by the student demands its active role, from a process of elaboration and development of an object of own research and correspondence with the study program. In addition, the only requirements that condition the Feasible Project are that it synthesizes its interest and that it involves an approach based on the understanding of the basic stages with techniques and instruments that allow them to be aware of the real needs and of their contribution from a viable proposal.

This proposal entails the acquisition of high levels of autonomy of the researcher, who must reconcile his vision and transformation in the thematic domain treated, the theoretical reference enriched in the postgraduate subjects and the practical instances in which he will generate his proposal.

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